

To estimate field parasitism by the nematode, weekly collections of BPH infesting paddy were made. About half of the BPH collected were dissected; the others were reared in the laboratory. The table shows parasitism.

This Mermithid was also reared from

field collected *Sogatella furcifera* and *Nephotettix nigropictus*.

The Mirid *Cyrtorhinus lividipennis*, an important predator of the BPH, was parasitized by another Mermithid which may represent a new genus. However, it was scarce.

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Occurrence of brown planthopper on rice in West Bengal, India

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In West Bengal, the brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens* was first noted as a serious pest of summer (boro) rice in 1973 at Khanakul, Hooghly district. Epidemics of the pest have since appeared

regularly in ever-larger areas. Recently the infestation has spread to other rice-growing areas of West Bengal, particularly river and coastal belts. The BPH has also been recorded on main winter (kharif or aman) rice, but there damage is less.

The main rice-growing area of Khanakul is low-lying and basinlike; water from two rivers and a number of drainage channels are impounded there. Summer rice is the main crop because land is submerged from July to November.

The initial attack is by immigrant macropterous insects, which produce both macropterous and brachypterous forms, during late February and March. Hopperburn is noticed in April. The pest disappears in mid-May, at the time of rice harvest. All the high yielding photoperiod-insensitive rice varieties are attacked. But some local rice varieties of lower yield potential that are transplanted earlier escape damage.

Populations of leafhoppers and planthoppers in Egypt from 1973 to 1975, as indicated by sweep-net samples

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Samples of leafhoppers and planthoppers were taken weekly with a sweep net (1 00 double strokes/sample) throughout the April to November rice-growing seasons from 1973 to 1975 at Kafr-el-Sheikh, Egypt. Eight cicadellid species, six delphacids, and only one cixiid were found. But two dominant species were caught in great numbers - *Balclutha hortensis* and *Sogatella vibix*. Next in abundance were *Nephotettix modulatus* and *Sogatella furcifera* (see table).

The number of leafhoppers and planthoppers increased gradually from year to year. In the three successive seasons of 1973, 1974, and 1975, cicadellids averaged 44.5, 258.6, and 929.5 insects/100 strokes, respectively; delphacids, 17.3, 271.4, and 623.1/100 strokes. In 1973, populations of most

cicadellids peaked in July and August; in 1974 and 1975, they peaked in October and November. Populations of all the delphacid species, however, peaked

in October and November in the 3 sampling years.

The average sex ratio of various species from 1973 to 1975 was near equality

Population density and sex ratio of leafhoppers and planthoppers in sweep-net samples taken weekly throughout the rice-growing season (Apr.–Nov.) at Kafr-el-Sheikh, Egypt, 1973 to 1975.

Family and species	Mean no./100 strokes			Peak no./100 strokes ^a			Males (av %)
	1973	1974	1975	1973	1974	1975	
FAMILY CICADELLIDAE							
<i>Balclutha hortensis</i>	18.7	238.7	875.4	32.8	807.0	2955.2	46.3
<i>Nephotettix modulatus</i>	6.3	3.2	42.0	14.4	13.8	166.4	54.1
<i>Cicadulina bipunctella</i>							
<i>zeae</i>	9.5	14.7	6.5	19.5	43.3	19.3	46.8
<i>Empoasca decipiens</i>	3.6	0.8	2.8	10.3	3.0	13.8	43.7
<i>Macrostelus sexnotatus</i>	5.5	0.7	1.0	16.0	2.0	3.8	28.7
<i>Exitianus taeniaceps</i>	0.9	0.5	1.3	2.8	1.5	7.3	62.8
<i>Recilia schmidtgeni</i>	0.0	0.0	0.6	—	—	2.7	—
<i>Neoliturus haematoceps</i>	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.2	0.0	—
Total	44.5	258.6	929.5	86.0	853.0	3136.8	—
FAMILY DELPHACIDAE							
<i>Sogatella vibix</i>	12.8	250.0	593.5	24.0	1400.0	2507.2	54.5
<i>Sogatella furcifera</i>	3.1	19.3	26.6	9.5	116.0	124.4	55.2
<i>Toya nigeriensis</i>	0.9	0.8	2.0	5.0	4.0	5.3	47.9
<i>Falctoya aglauros</i>	0.4	1.3	0.8	3.0	6.0	2.0	75.4
<i>Matutinus iphias</i>	0.0	0.1	0.2	—	—	—	—
<i>Dopidocephala elegans</i>	0.0	0.0	0.2	—	—	—	—
Total	17.3	271.4	623.1	41.5	1526.0	2638.0	—
FAMILY CIXIIDAE							
<i>Oliarus frontalis</i>	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.0	2.0	3.0	75.0

^aMonthly average.